

EXPERIENCES OF THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION IN ENHANCING FINANCIAL LITERACY SKILLS IN SCHOOLS

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Keywords

Education system of the Russian Federation, Ministry of Finance, primary education, financial games, financial literacy, financial literacy center, school education, economic sciences, financial knowledge

Abstract

This article analyzes the financial literacy programs of the Russian Federation and explores ways to adapt them to the conditions of Uzbekistan. Emphasizing that financial literacy has a positive impact on economic stability and well-being of the population, the study notes the need for cooperation between the public and private sectors, the organization of special courses and training in educational institutions, as well as the use of modern technology. Suggestions and recommendations developed on the basis of the experience of the Russian Federation are of great importance in the formation of practical programs aimed at improving financial literacy in the school system of Uzbekistan.

Introduction

Financial literacy as an important component of education is included in school curricula of many developed and strong developing countries. In many countries, the availability of credit resources at low interest rates encourages households to borrow more. As a result, the debt burden of households is increasing year by year on a global scale. Therefore, today, teaching young people to manage their personal budgets by providing them with financial knowledge from school years, giving them basic understanding of investment, insurance and other financial instruments is seen as the main means of achieving financial stability and prosperity for young people in the future. We will closely familiarize ourselves with the pedagogical experience of the state of the Russian Federation, which has a huge historical experience in this regard.

In the Russian Federation, studies are regularly conducted at the state level to assess the knowledge of students. In the Russian Federation, a unique school providing financial literacy education was formed. Studying the experience of this school is not difficult because most of the population of Uzbekistan knows the Russian language to some extent. Based on the research results, new approaches are developed for effective organization of pedagogical processes. It is the study of the educational experience of the Russian Federation that allows you to master the educational methods that are considered the most effective.

Literature review

Financial literacy is now an important factor in achieving global economic stability and prosperity. In this regard, the scientific research and literature analysis conducted in the Russian Federation allows for the development of effective strategies for increasing financial literacy.

Galina Kovaleva, Elena Rutkovskaya, Nikita Kolachev, Anastasia Polovnikova studied in their research based on PISA 2018 data that the literacy of schoolchildren also depends on socio-economic background. [1]

The role of schools in the Russian Federation in the formation of financial literacy in the country was analyzed by the Social and Humanitarian Education Center (RAE). In the course of these analyses, the subjects and other programs focused on financial and economic knowledge in schools were studied and proposals were developed to eliminate the shortcomings. [2]

In the study "Development and Education of Financial Literacy in Russia" conducted by the Ministry of Finance of Russia and the World Bank, an analysis of the effectiveness of financial knowledge in practice was carried out. [3]

N. Kuzina in his scientific research entitled "Development of Financial Security" conducted a scientific research on acquiring legal knowledge and skills in financial operations to a certain extent in addition to financial literacy.

The PISA research group of the Russian Federation also analyzed the level of financial literacy of students in the country and conducted analyzes to identify shortcomings in the practical application of financial knowledge. [4]

Analysis of the current state of financial literacy in Uzbekistan, existing problems and opportunities shows the need to strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors. The reports submitted by the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan provide information on the measures implemented to increase the level of financial knowledge of the population. Research conducted by the World Bank [4] detailed proposed strategies for improving financial skills in Uzbekistan.

An analysis of effective strategies and approaches to increase financial literacy includes strengthening public and private sector cooperation, using modern technologies, and implementing interactive methods. The research of Lusardi et al. [5] shows the role of financial knowledge in the fight against social and economic inequality, and it is emphasized that economic inequality can be reduced by increasing this knowledge.

Methods

In our research, we study the best foreign experiences in improving financial literacy of schoolchildren by teaching them financial knowledge through various games. We will closely familiarize ourselves with the pedagogical experiences of the Russian Federation, which has a huge historical experience in this regard. There are several reasons for studying the educational experience of the Russian Federation in providing financial literacy education among schoolchildren. The main task of the education system of the Russian Federation is to develop a national strategy for financial literacy and integrate it into practice, along with increasing financial literacy among the general public. A center aimed at increasing financial literacy in a particular country under the Ministry of Finance is also performing its activities. In addition, the educational system of the Russian Federation is one of the leaders among the CIS countries, and in a certain sense, it is possible to know that the experience of teaching financial literacy is high in the educational system of this country. Games can be selected by teachers depending on the age, level of knowledge, material and technical base of the school and subject. Of course, this serves to facilitate and speed up the process of providing financial education to students studying in primary and secondary schools in Uzbekistan.

Results

The results obtained during the research show that it is very important to study the experiences of the Russian Federation in providing financial literacy education in the schools of Uzbekistan and introduce what is considered suitable into school education. Also, this process helps to identify training methods and save time and resources. It is necessary to organize special courses and trainings to increase financial literacy in schools. These courses should be adapted for students of different ages. In addition, it is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors to increase financial literacy. This process should include the use of modern technologies and interactive methods.

Analysis

The Russian Federation is also a country with a special place in terms of school education. Russia ranks 27th in the world in terms of education.[5] The level of financial literacy of the population of the Russian Federation is quite low. The debt burden ratio of the population is increasing, and the number of bankrupt individuals who owe money to banks is also increasing. Many citizens do not take into account the

risks associated with various financial instruments, cannot assess the risks for their financial decisions and possible losses in the financial markets. A small number of Russian citizens are able to properly manage their personal funds, that is, they have the opportunity to generate passive income by using financial instruments wisely. They plan their income and expenses, analyze financial services, and create long-term savings for unexpected situations. [6]

Taking this into account, a number of tools are used to teach financial literacy, financial development and management. These tools are designed to teach financial skills and concepts to students.

In the Russian Federation, since April 2016, the "Federal Methodological Center for Financial Literacy in the General and Secondary Education System" was opened under the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation. A number of main tasks have been assigned to this center, these tasks serve to spread financial literacy among the population in addition to teaching financial literacy to students in school education in the federation. The main tasks of the federal methodological center are as follows: [7]

- to ensure a systematic approach to the development of citizens' financial literacy and financial culture, to increase the level of financial security, including financial cyber security;

- developing and approving the criteria and requirements of educational programs aimed at increasing the level of financial literacy and financial culture, monitoring the quality of implemented programs;

- Introduction of educational programs, educational and methodological materials that ensure the formation of financial culture in the educational system of the Russian Federation, updating them in a timely manner

- conducting the "High Standard" All-Russian Olympiad for schoolchildren in the profile of financial literacy;

- identify and promote the best pedagogical practices of teaching financial literacy by holding professional competitions for teachers who teach educational programs that include elements of financial literacy;

- tasks such as analyzing public opinion on financial literacy and financial culture issues, studying society's needs for learning in the field of financial literacy and financial culture, and ensuring timely response to relevant appeals are assigned.

Open information about the center and the results of its practical experience is constantly published on their web pages. The web page contains examples of methodological developments, educational programs, webinars, and open classes developed by the center. [8]

Separate topics have been developed for each grade and based on the age categories of students, and video instructions on these topics have also been uploaded to the web page. These topics were developed based on the subjects taught to the students and the topics in the subjects of finance and economics.

Since 2017, financial literacy Olympiads have been continuously held by the center. Such an initiative was put forward by the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation. The main purpose of conducting the Olympiad is to increase the interest of schoolchildren in scientific and research activities in the field of finance, popularize scientific knowledge about the functioning mechanism of financial markets, provide professional guidance to schoolchildren, and acquire the skills of rational management of personal finances. Olympiad also fulfills an important educational function for students, that is, it helps students to spread financial knowledge among their parents and acquire safe financial knowledge. Students of grades 7-11 and students of secondary special educational organizations (technical institutes, colleges) who have not completed their studies in the educational programs of secondary general education will participate in the Financial Literacy Olympiad. For students, participating in this Olympiad can not only test their knowledge of financial literacy, but also provide them with privileges to enter universities. Annual questions and tasks of the Olympiad are constantly uploaded to the website of the center, which serves as a basis for mastering additional financial literacy in the teaching process for students or teachers who have not participated in the Olympiad or who want to participate in the future. [9]

School education in Russia is regulated by the state and includes a system of training students at different levels. The school education system in Russia has its own methods and programs and consists of several stages.

1. Primary education classes

Primary education is intended for age groups from 6-7 years old to 10-11 years old. Primary education is designed to motivate students to study, develop creative and artistic abilities of students, and ensure that they get to know the world. At this stage, students are taught subjects such as mathematics and logical thinking to improve financial literacy.

Several financial literacy games have been developed for elementary grades. "Young financier", "Financial theater business game", "How to spend money", "Young tax collectors", "How to protect ourselves from financial risks?" There are financial games like [9]

Secondary education classes

Secondary education is intended for age groups from 10-11 to 15-16 years, and is intended for students to receive general secondary education. Secondary education classes, educational processes are organized in order to provide students with a general secondary education, develop analytical thinking skills and adapt to changes. Students studying at this age level are taught subjects such as financial mathematics, economics, and financial management.

There are also financial games for the development of financial literacy for secondary education classes: "Entrepreneurship", "Family budget" business game,

"Financial market" games, "Creating a personal business plan", and "Consumer rights protection" business game. [10]

1. Classes of higher education

Higher secondary education is intended for age groups from 15-16 to 17-18 years old, and they are trained mainly to prepare for higher education. Upper secondary education classes are organized educational processes in order to prepare their students for higher education and to gain wider knowledge in their chosen field. Higher education classes are taught financial subjects such as probability theory, business and finance.

The use of such games in the classroom will help students acquire financial knowledge, but some games may require a certain level of infrastructure and material technical base.

The following methods are used in practice for teaching financial literacy in Russian schools:

- Financial games and simulations.

Financial games and simulations help students learn and apply financial skills. These games cover topics such as planning financial expenses and generating passive income.

- Financial education classes. Financial education classes help students learn financial concepts both theoretically and practically. These lessons lead to understanding financial documents, calculating financial data, building funds in the form of savings, investing and other financial skills.

- By creating financial subgroups. Financial small groups allow students to build financial experiences and develop their financial skills. Such small groups organize teamwork and negotiations on financial relations, financial skills training.

- Contests on business and financial innovations. Choices and guides on business and financial innovation help students develop innovative thinking in finance. These competitions give students the opportunity to develop new business ideas, create business plans and think about other financial questions. [10]

In Russia, high-quality education for students is being provided by production enterprises, the Central Bank of Russia and many financial institutions, and teachers are actively involved in the production process. Students can choose games depending on their age, level of knowledge, the material and technical base of the school and the topic. These games can be found on the websites of the Central Bank of Russia and many commercial banks, as well as on many educational websites and platforms.

Develop measures to develop literacy, which is specific to Russian production, and to help students develop and improve their knowledge in school lessons. The Russian system also has similar stages to the school education system. In Russia, it is being implemented through several centers to increase literacy. The "Investment in the Future" (Vklad v budushee) project is a production direction at Sberbank. On this

platform of the center, the all-Russian production literacy is analyzed by year, in addition, competitions, science Olympiads, seminar trainings held among students throughout the Russian Federation are constantly covered, and scientific methodological programs are posted on the website. Under the project, science teachers also regularly post production programs on the website for experts in the development of modern education, and these programs are used to improve current disagreements in the lessons of continuing literacy in schools. Another convenient aspect is the constant posting of literature on finance and economics in the electronic library, which is very convenient for all website users. All products, literature, and question sets under this project are free for website users. [12]

Figure 1: Investment plan for the future educational website.

The Bank of Russia of the Russian Federation has developed interactive financial games for schoolchildren of each level in accordance with the topics of school textbooks to improve their financial and economic knowledge, and has posted a scenario for each game on how and under what conditions to play them. This platform was specially developed for educational organizations, namely for schoolchildren, for vacationers of children's health camps, for students of organizations for children left without parental care in orphanages. Within the framework of the project, financial literacy games introduce the youngest participants to the basics of financial literacy, and senior students consolidate the knowledge gained in financial literacy lessons. The games posted on the platform allow you to consolidate the knowledge gained in financial literacy lessons, individual scenarios have been prepared for each game and a detailed description of the game process, as well as the roles of the participants in the game, are also written in detail. A game specialist has included enough additional information to play a game on the topic recommended for the educator. One of the most important aspects is that the games uploaded to the platform are notable for not

requiring financially expensive and complex props, and are designed to be very convenient for all users. [12]

Figure 2: Financial literacy games educational website by the Central Bank of Russia.

Another unique aspect of the development of financial literacy in the Russian Federation is that separate projects aimed at increasing financial literacy have been developed for the regions included in the Federation. The program for increasing the level of financial literacy of the population of the Kaliningrad region began in 2011. The project was launched by the Kaliningrad Finance Department within the framework of the project “Increasing the level of financial literacy of the population and developing financial education in the Russian Federation” of the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation and the World Bank. The main goal of this project is to increase the level of financial literacy of the population of the region, to form a financial culture among Russian citizens, to improve the efficiency of proper and targeted management of funds, and to protect the rights of its citizens. [13]

Discussion

In the course of writing this scientific work, the following main questions arose regarding the process of providing financial literacy education in Uzbekistan, using the experience of the Russian Federation. How can the Russian Federation organize the provision of financial literacy education from school age in the conditions of Uzbekistan to achieve high efficiency? How can young people be involved in their free time from classes to increase their level of financial literacy from school age? What do we need to learn from foreign experiences in this regard? Scientifically based answers to these questions were formed during the implementation of this research.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it is very important to study the experience of the Russian Federation in providing financial literacy education in Uzbek schools and introduce

those that are considered suitable for Uzbekistan into school education. Studying the experience of the Russian Federation will save financial resources and time spent on pedagogical research aimed at identifying effective methods of providing financial education. The introduction of current educational methods and techniques that are already available in world practice into the Uzbek education system will help increase the level of financial literacy of the future generation, and ultimately, raise a financially stable and prosperous generation.

The following proposals were developed during the study.

- It is recommended to use modern technologies and interactive methods when teaching financial knowledge to students. This includes teaching digital financial skills.

- It is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the public and private sectors to improve financial literacy. Financial institutions and educational institutions can jointly organize various events and competitions.

- It is necessary to create financial educational resources. This can be done through books, textbooks, online courses and various games.

These recommendations are of great importance in the formation of practical programs aimed at increasing financial literacy in the school education system of Uzbekistan. Programs and approaches developed based on the experience of the Russian Federation will be effective in increasing the financial knowledge and skills of the younger generation. Based on these recommendations, reforming the education system, improving curricula and implementing measures aimed at increasing financial literacy will make a positive contribution to the economic development of Uzbekistan.

References

1. <https://vo.hse.ru/article/view/15787>
2. Russian Schoolchildren Financial Literacy As A Socialization Factor In The Information Age
3. Financial Literacy and Financial Capability: Interdependence of Concepts and Possibilities to Form Them in a School Course of Mathematics
4. Financial Literacy Of The Russian Schoolchildren: Development Problems
5. In the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment of Financial Literacy (2018), Russia ranked 27th among participating countries.
6. From the article by Yulia Butrina, Associate Professor of South Ural University, Financial literacy should become a mandatory subject in school, 2021.13.09 <https://fmc.hse.ru/ocentre>
7. <https://fmc.hse.ru/openlessons>
8. <https://fmc.hse.ru/olymp>
9. SberBank. Investment for the future website <https://vbudushee.ru/>
10. Official website of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation, edu.gov.ru
11. <https://doligra.ru/about>

12. <https://www.fingram39.ru>